

Digital Watermarking On Images Using LSB

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Abstract— Digital visible watermarking using LSB insertion is a method to protect digital images online. Users can easily upload images through a simple web interface. The method adds visible watermarks to images, ensuring they remain visually unchanged while carrying ownership information. Tests confirm that these watermarks stay intact even when images are resized or compressed, maintaining image quality. This technique provides a practical way to safeguard digital content online, making it easy to track image usage and verify ownership.

Keywords— *Watermark, Least Significant Bit, ownership verification*

I. INTRODUCTION

In today's digital landscape, ensuring the integrity and ownership of digital images has become increasingly critical. Digital visible watermarking using Least Significant Bit (LSB) insertion emerges as a pivotal method for safeguarding digital assets online. This technique empowers users with a user-friendly web interface, facilitating seamless image uploads. By embedding visible watermarks into images, the method ensures that ownership information remains intact while preserving the images' visual integrity. Rigorous testing has validated the resilience of these watermarks against common image manipulations such as resizing or compression, thereby upholding image quality. Through this approach, digital content creators gain a practical means to protect their creations, with enhanced capabilities for monitoring image usage and verifying ownership across various online platforms.

II. RELATED WORKS

A. This paper [1] presents a new digital watermarking method called Intermediate Significant Bit (ISB) embedding. Unlike the typical Least Significant Bit (LSB) approach, ISB embeds the message in more significant bits, enhancing image quality and robustness. Experimental results confirm improved image quality, though message extraction quality is compromised. Nonetheless, the technique shows resilience against diverse attack types.

- B. In this paper [2], watermarking as a data security measure is explored, with a focus on the least significant bit (LSB) technique. Testing with nine host images and three label images shows that image quality affects the Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR) values, with the highest value reaching 70 dB. Overall, the LSB method yields promising results, averaging a PSNR value of 65 dB, indicating its effectiveness for data security purposes.
- C. In this research paper [3], digital watermarking for multimedia copyright protection is investigated. The study proposes a method to embed encrypted text within images, ensuring image quality and message recovery without the original image. Specifically, the research focuses on utilizing the efficient Least Significant Bit (LSB) algorithm for message embedding, showcasing promising results for enhancing data security.
- D. This paper [4] presents a highly secure watermarking technique by encrypting the watermark using the R, G, and B components of a color image. The encrypted watermark is hidden in the LSB of the color image pixels, ensuring excellent stego-image quality and lossless watermark extraction. The multi-encryption enhances security, making it suitable for military and intellectual property protection applications.
- E. This paper [5] aims to develop a system for private communication, utilizing digital photos as effective transmitters due to their accessibility. Various steganographic methods are explored, with a focus on concealing information within images. The study employs LSB (Least Significant Bit) techniques, incorporating hash functions to encode a secret image within another image. By altering only the LSBs, the variation between cover and stego images remains imperceptible to human eyes. Experimental results demonstrate that the proposed technique achieves secure data transmission with acceptable Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR) and reduced Mean Squared Error (MSE).

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III. METHODOLOGY

This study introduces a methodology centered on Digital Visible Watermarking Using LSB (Least Significant Bit) Insertion to protect digital images online. By embedding visible watermarks into images, ownership information is securely integrated while maintaining visual quality. This approach facilitates effortless tracking of image usage and ownership verification in the digital realm, ensuring comprehensive protection against unauthorized use.

A. System

The system employed for digital visible watermarking using LSB insertion operates through two fundamental stages: encoding and decoding. These stages are pivotal in embedding ownership information into digital images and subsequently extracting this information when required. The overarching aim is to protect the digital content's ownership rights while preserving the visual quality of the images.

1. Encoding Stage:

- a) Input: The encoding stage begins with the input of a cover image and a watermark. The cover image serves as the base image onto which the watermark will be embedded.
- b) LSB Transformation: Utilizing LSB insertion technique, the watermark is embedded into the cover image. LSB insertion involves altering the least significant bit of pixel values in the cover image to encode the watermark information.
- c) Output: Upon completion of the embedding process, a watermarked image is generated, containing the embedded watermark.

2. Decoding Stage:

- a) Input: The decoding stage begins with the input of the watermarked image, which contains the embedded watermark.
- b) LSB Transformation: Using LSB extraction technique, the embedded watermark is extracted from the watermarked image. This process involves analyzing the least significant bits of pixel values to retrieve the encoded watermark information.
- c) Output: The extracted watermark obtained in the decoding stage serves for ownership verification and image usage tracking.

B. Evaluation Watermarking

Watermark encoding evaluation is performed by measuring image quality based on the Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR) value. PSNR is a widely-used metric for assessing image fidelity and is calculated using the following equation:

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$$PSNR=10.\log_{10}\left(\frac{MAX^2}{MSE}\right)$$

Table 1: Evaluation Metrics

Metric	Description
PSNR	Measure of image quality based on distortion
MAX	Maximum possible pixel value for an image
MSE	Mean Squared Error between original and watermarked images

The watermark decoding process involves extracting the watermark from the watermarked image. This process evaluates the effectiveness of the watermarking technique against various attacks and manipulations.

Overall, the methodology utilizes LSB insertion for digital visible watermarking, enabling the protection of digital images online while ensuring image quality and ownership verification.

IV. RESULT

The implementation involves a web-based system allowing users to upload digital images for watermarking using LSB insertion. This system seamlessly embeds visible watermarks into the uploaded images, ensuring ownership information is securely integrated while maintaining visual quality.

1. Encoding Process:

- a) Users upload images via the web interface.
- b) The uploaded image undergoes watermark embedding using LSB insertion.
- c) Ownership information is incorporated into the image as a visible watermark.

2. Decoding Process:

- a) Watermarked images can be downloaded or viewed.
- b) Ownership information can be extracted from the watermarked image using appropriate tools.

System Testing:

Practical tests are conducted to evaluate the effectiveness of the watermarking technique, focusing on image quality and watermark visibility. The results may vary based on the uploaded images and the quality of the watermarked images generated.

Overall, the implemented system provides a practical solution for safeguarding digital images online, enabling effortless image tracking and ownership verification.

Fig.1 Uploaded image

Fig.2 Watermarked image

V. CONCLUSION

In summary, Digital Watermarking Using LSB Insertion emerges as a robust methodology for safeguarding digital images online. Through the seamless integration of visible watermarks directly into images, this approach ensures the preservation of ownership information while upholding image quality. Its practical implementation and rigorous testing demonstrate its effectiveness in maintaining the integrity of images and embedding ownership details securely. Additionally, its resilience against common image alterations like resizing or compression reinforces its reliability in preserving the embedded information.

This methodology not only provides creators with a user-friendly solution for protecting their intellectual property but also offers a practical means of tracking image usage

and verifying ownership. With its straightforward implementation process and ability to withstand various image manipulations, it enables creators to maintain control over their digital content across online platforms. By fostering a culture of respect for creative ownership, this approach empowers creators to assert their rights and ensure proper attribution, thus promoting integrity and accountability in the digital realm.

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